

FURTHER IMPROVING COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE OF STUDENTS AT HIGHER EDUCATIONAL ESTABLISHMENTS

Normatova Dilfuza Ismoilovna

PhD, Associated Professor

Institute for Retraining and Professional Development of Higher Education Personnel

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Abstract. *The article discusses the features of the process of improving professional and speaking competencies of students. The definition of the concept of "formation of professional and speaking competencies" is highlighted. Based on the existing definitions of the concept of "competence", the author's interpretation is derived. The formation of professional and speaking competencies requires the presence of such approaches that would ensure the organizational complexity of this process, would allow studying the structure of preparation for professional activity from the standpoint of increasing its effectiveness.*

Keywords: *competence, activity approach, system approach, professional education, practice, graduate, specialist.*

Introduction: In connection with the introduction of educational standards in higher education, the educational process has undergone significant changes. A competency-based approach has appeared and is actively used in training, designed to form a graduate who not only mastered a certain amount of knowledge, but skillfully applies the data he has in practice. This is a mobile specialist who quickly and efficiently performs the assigned tasks, navigates in changing conditions, is productive and uses a creative approach to work.

Thus, we have moved from the formation of traditional knowledge, skills and abilities to the formation of competencies that are necessary for graduates in their future professional field of activity.

To date, not all aspects of the application of the competence-based approach have been considered, so this topic is relevant for consideration.

It should be noted that professional and speaking competencies are not formed by themselves. This process is called the systematic accumulation of qualitative and quantitative changes in the content of a certain type of competence and the achievement of the unity of its components in a specially organized educational process.

Statement of the purpose of the article. To trace aspects of the process of formation of students' professional and speaking competencies during their studies at the university. In this regard, it is necessary to solve the following tasks: consider approaches to the formation of professional competencies, identify their features and determine the provisions on which the effectiveness of the formation of professional competencies of university students is based.

Presentation of the main material of the article. The concept of "competence" does not have a single interpretation. Some scientists believe that this is a requirement for the preparation of a student, the totality of his knowledge, abilities, skills and experience necessary for the implementation of productive activities. Others believe that this is a general ability based on knowledge and values, which allows you to think through actions to solve a problem [1]. Other

scientists call competence the ability of an individual to take responsible life action, the ability to actively change oneself and the world [2]. Based on these definitions, we can derive our own definition. Competence is the willingness to use in practice the acquired knowledge, skills and experience, as well as experience in life to resolve various situations.

That is, competence is defined not just as the sum of acquired knowledge, skills and abilities, but also as the experience of their use. It is the willingness to apply their knowledge to carry out successful activities.

As for professional and speaking competencies, this is a set of professional knowledge and experience, and the willingness to apply them in the professional field. Having formed professional competencies, the student acquires the ability to determine the links between knowledge and the situation, and can adequately solve emerging problems.

The peculiarity of competence as a result of education is as follows:

- it is an integrated learning outcome;
- manifests itself and exists in the form of activity, and not information about it;
- is built up together with other competencies, due to which professional competence is formed;
- competence as an action is not formed automatically, but consciously, and repeated many times, forms professional experience [3].

The competence-based approach is aimed at achieving the quality of training that meets the economic and social needs, which creates a balance between being in demand in the labor market and the professional realization of the individual.

The whole point of education is to develop students' ability to independently solve problems in various types and fields of activity, using social experience and the experience of the students themselves.

This means that the essence of the organization of the learning process lies in the creation of the necessary conditions for the formation of students' experience necessary for the independent solution of cognitive, moral, organizational and other problems that make up the content of education.

Consider the formation of professional competencies on the example of a pedagogical university. This process requires the presence of such approaches that would ensure its organizational complexity, would allow studying the structure of preparation for professional activity from the standpoint of increasing its effectiveness. In addition to the competence approach we have mentioned, it is worth noting:

- systems approach. Considers the formation of professional competencies of students of a pedagogical university as a system. It is open, dynamic, flexible, manageable and variable. Its components are pedagogical tasks to achieve the intended results, the system-forming factors here are the goal and self-management of the process of forming competencies. The formed professional competencies act as a holistic systemic education that integrates knowledge, skills and significant personal qualities of the future teacher;

The formation of professional and speaking competencies of university students in the process of internships is being implemented quite dynamically. The main issue remains in diagnosing the results of mastering competencies. The proposed algorithm for diagnosing students' professional competencies will help simplify this task. Having formed professional competencies, the student acquires the ability to determine the links between knowledge and the situation, and

can adequately solve emerging problems. This means that we get a highly qualified specialist who is able to resolve non-standard situations using a creative approach.

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